

PREFATORY NOTE

The 3rd International Babylon Conference on Clinical and Experimental Pharmacological Research: prioritising drug safety, *in silico* drug screening, and the reliability assessment of novel *in vitro* tools for pharmacodynamic simulations

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This third iteration of the International Babylon Conference on Clinical and Experimental Pharmacological Research marks a decisive step in the maturation of one of the most important events in Iraq's emerging pharmacological research ecosystem. Building on the foundations laid by the first two conferences (taking place in 2024 and 2025) – each of which had two main objectives, namely the mapping of the Iraqi pharmacological research and priorities, and the facilitation of the establishment of international collaborations in the field [1,2] – this year's conference advances the conversation into domains that are rapidly reshaping global drug development and use. In this third conference, focus shifts toward three interdependent pillars of pharmacological research: drug safety, *in silico* drug screening, and the assessment of novel *in vitro* tools for the undertaking of more reliable pharmacodynamic simulations. Among these pillars, drug safety remains a cornerstone of therapeutic development, and this conference successfully highlights the importance of a systematic evaluation of toxicity, off-target effects, and population-specific risk factors in both Iraq and abroad. The second pillar – *in*

in silico drug screening – responds directly to the calls for the adoption of innovative methodologies capable of reducing the experimental (and the cost-associated) burden while increasing predictive power. Given that the available computational screening platforms can allow researchers to interrogate vast chemical libraries, model ligand–receptor interactions, and forecast pharmacokinetic behaviour with unprecedented efficiency, their effective integration into the Iraqi research workflows represents both a technological leap as well as a pragmatic response to the current resource constraints. Finally, the third pillar highlighted in this year's conference is the reliability assessment of novel *in vitro* pharmacodynamic tools, and reflects the conference scientific committees' longstanding emphasis on methodological robustness. As the credibility of preclinical experimental findings depends largely on the physiological relevance and the reproducibility of the “models” employed, the rigorous and ongoing (re)validation of the latter becomes increasingly essential and should go hand-in-hand with the pursuit of novelty. This year, the conference takes place at the College of Pharmacy

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of the University of Babylon, in Hillah, Iraq, on the 29th and 30th of June 2026, under the auspices of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research of the Republic of Iraq, the University of Babylon and its College of Pharmacy, as well as Madenat Alelem University and its College of Pharmacy. The conference proceedings are hereby graciously hosted by *Colloquia Erudita*; a recently established, open-access series of proceedings published by St Cuthbert Press Ltd (Stanley, England, UK). In this volume, our editorial interventions have been minimal while aiming to ensure that the proceedings abstracts maintain the levels of accuracy, clarity, and consistency that have characterized the conference's previous proceedings. To this end, we are grateful to all conference contributors for their collaboration and patience, and we hope that this volume will serve as a testament to the efforts of the conference's steering and scientific committees (led by the Dean of the College of Pharmacy of the University of Babylon, Professor Hussam W. Al-Humadi) to strengthen scientific dialogue and to advance pharmacological research at a local level and in line with international standards.

Keywords

adverse effects; computational screening; *in vitro* methodology; Iraq; pharmacology

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Conflicts of interest statement

RJA, AK, and AZ are a professor, a visiting professor, and an honorary professor, respectively, at the Univer-

sity of Babylon. Moreover, RJA and AK serve as series editors of the hosting open-access series (*Colloquia Erudita*), while AZ holds a majority ownership stake in its publisher (St Cuthbert Press Ltd). In order to eliminate any potential conflict-of-interest concerns, the publisher has waived the entirety of the publication fees for this volume of proceedings, ensuring that the University of Babylon bore no financial cost whatsoever for its production or dissemination.

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